

The Impact of Spiritual, Social, And Emotional Intelligence on the Performance of SMEs in the Covid-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT: Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are an important part of the economic system in Indonesia, this can be seen from the number compared to large-scale industrial enterprises. SMEs in their position have advantages compared to large-scale businesses, one of the advantages is being able to absorb more labor and accelerate the process of equitable development. However, currently, SMEs are experiencing problems in achieving better performance. These obstacles do not only come from within the SMEs organization but also from outside. Internal factors are factors that come from the work environment such as organizational culture, attitudes, and actions of colleagues as well as the organizational structure of the SMEs. Internal factors include intelligence it has, there are several bits of intelligence in humans, including emotional intelligence, social intelligence, and spiritual intelligence. Therefore, this study aims to determine the effect of spiritual intelligence, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence on SMEs actors during the Covid-19 period. This research is a quantitative study with a population of small and medium enterprises. The sampling method is purposive sampling, which was conducted using 90 samples. The approach of data analysis with multiple linear regression. The tool used is a regression with IBM SPSS 25 software. The results showed that spiritual intelligence, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence affected the performance of SMEs during the Covid-19 period.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19, Emotional, Enterprises, Performance, Spiritual, Social.

INTRODUCTION

Small, and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are an important part of the economic system in Indonesia, this can be seen from the number compared to large-scale industrial enterprises. SMEs in their position have advantages compared to large-scale businesses, one of the advantages is the ability to absorb more labor and accelerate the process of equitable development (Bayu and Sukartha, 2019). In its journey, SMEs are now increasingly gaining positions in the Indonesian economic arena so that SMEs are used as a means of realizing national development policies (Friday 2018). Seeing this fact is clear evidence that SMEs are increasingly gaining positions in the Indonesian economy. However, SMEs in Indonesia are not perfect as expected because SMEs are still facing problems. The basic problem experienced is that the improvement in the quality of human resources (HR) for SMEs actors has not been optimal and has an impact on SMEs performance (Jumadi, 2019). In addition, SMEs are currently experiencing problems with the emergence of Covid-19. Covid-19 has an impact on the economic slowdown in the SMEs sector, this is under (Pratiwi, 2020). The same thing was conveyed by (Nalini, 2021) who stated that Covid-19 had an impact on SMEs. According to (Amri, 2020) that the decline in the tourism and SMEs sectors reached 27%. However, despite the Covid-19 outbreak, every business, including SMEs, still wants to achieve its best performance goals.

Performance is one measure of the success of a business, according to (Ranto, 2007), performance is the result of management activities in carrying out their duties and responsibilities towards public accountability, both in the form of success and shortcomings. Performance is the achievement of an organization in a certain accounting period which is measured by comparison with various previously established standards (Srimindarti, 2006). Meanwhile, according to (Ludin et al, 2018), that performance is one measure in determining the success of a person or a company in running its business. Performance can be influenced by internal and external factors. External factors derived from the work environment include attitudes, organizational culture, the actions of colleagues, and organizational structure. Internal factors include intelligence, there are several bits of intelligence in humans, including intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence. If this intelligence can function effectively, it will display outstanding work results (Choiriah, 2013).

The results of the study (Goleman, 2006) explain that intellectual intelligence only accounts for 20 percent of success and 80 percent comes from other forces including emotional intelligence. In addition to intelligence, emotional intelligence can also affect performance. According to (Jumadi, 2020), emotional intelligence can be used to describe several skills related to the accuracy of judgments about emotions of oneself, others, and the ability to manage feelings to motivate, plan and achieve life goals. Meanwhile, Boyatzis (1999) and Chermis (1998), explained that employees who have emotional intelligence can produce higher-quality performance. This is also supported by research (Ratnasari et al, 2020) which states that emotional intelligence affects employee performance.

Spiritual intelligence is the ability to understand and give spiritual meaning to life, good spiritual intelligence is expected to be better able to deal with various problems that will be faced. Spiritual intelligence also makes a person have determination, enthusiasm, confidence, and a positive and honest personality (Zohar & Marshall, 2001). A leader or manager with high spiritual intelligence will be pleasing to his employees because he has a high awareness of himself and his environment, has a patient and calm nature, and is not arrogant or arrogant. Spiritual intelligence is a necessary foundation for the effective functioning of intellectual and emotional intelligence. According to Floretta (2014), spiritual intelligence can integrate two other abilities previously mentioned, namely intellectual intelligence and emotional intelligence. Spiritual intelligence an important role in life and running a business and influences the SMEs performance (Jumadi, 2020). In addition to spiritual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and social intelligence are also expected to be able to improve the performance of SMEs. Based on this phenomenon, the research is interested in researching Spiritual, Emotional, and Social Intelligence on the performance of SMEs in the Covid-19 Period.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Spiritual Intelligence

According to Agustian (2001), spiritual intelligence is the ability to give the meaning of worship to every behavior and activity through steps and thoughts that are natural, towards a complete human being, and have an intergalactic and principled pattern of thinking only because of Allah. Bowell (2004) explains that spiritual intelligence is a process that can create a state of life in awe and wonder, interest, and enthusiasm, where the level of novelty of insight becomes more because new intelligence can flow continuously. Meanwhile, Zohar and Marshal (2007) explain that spiritual intelligence is a moral feeling, the ability to adjust rigid rules followed by an understanding of love, and an equal ability to be able to see when love and understanding reach their limits. Furthermore, Zohar and Marshal, (2007) explain that someone who has spiritual intelligence places their behavior and life in a more meaningful, broader, and richer context. This means that spiritual intelligence is the intelligence to assess a person's actions or way of life to be more valuable and meaningful.

According to Floretta (2014), spiritual intelligence is one of the foundations needed to be able to function intellectually and emotionally intelligence effectively. Spiritual intelligence can integrate two bits of intelligence, namely intellectual intelligence, and emotional intelligence, therefore spiritual intelligence becomes more important for every human being. Agustian (2016) defines spiritual intelligence as a moral sense, the ability to adjust rigid rules that are in line with understanding and love as well as an equal ability to see when love and understanding reach their limits, also allowing oneself to wrestle with good and evil, imagining what has not yet happened. and lift oneself from the low. Based on the above, it can be concluded that spiritual intelligence is the ability to live and accept all conditions experienced based on a sense of gratitude solely because of a sense of submission to Allah SWT. Humans who have spiritual intelligence will be transcendental and have a purpose in life solely because of Allah or depending on the Creator, therefore humans in their activities always carry the slogan Mamayu Hayuning Agomo (Jumadi, 2020). The results of research (Jumadi, 2020; Wibowo, 2017; Anasrulloh, 2017; Supriyanto & Troena, 2012,) explains that spiritual intelligence influences performance.

Social Intelligence

Social intelligence is the attitude of someone who shows that the individual has a social intelligence that can be seen in various forms, including affection, a sense of care for the surroundings, the ability to carry oneself, honesty, empathy, helping and appreciating, and caring for others in conditions. social environment. Social intelligence is one of the characteristics that must be possessed by everyone because it aims to form a person so that he becomes a human being, citizen, and good citizen (Sendayu 2011). Meanwhile, Honeywill (2015) explains that social intelligence is the ability to effectively navigate and negotiate in

interactions and the surrounding environment. According to Ganaie (2015) explaining that social intelligence is a combination of self-awareness with social awareness, the evolution of social beliefs, attitudes, capacities, and the ability to manage very complex social change. Based on this, it means that social intelligence is equivalent to interpersonal intelligence, one of the types of intelligence identified in the theory of multiple intelligences and closely related to the theory of mind. Social intelligence currently occupies a very important role when it comes to building a relationship that produces high productivity with a good level of harmonization as well. Relationships with friends, relatives, neighbors, co-workers, or also with superiors may run more and more pleasant if they can demonstrate several important elements of social intelligence Jumadi (2020).

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is the ability to feel emotions, receive and build emotions well, and understand emotions and emotional knowledge so that it can improve emotional and intellectual development. Emotional intelligence is in five main areas, namely, the ability to recognize one's emotions, manage one's emotions, motivate oneself, recognize other people's emotions, and the ability to build relationships with others. According to Goleman (2000), emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize one's feelings and the feelings of others, the ability to motivate oneself and manage emotions well oneself in dealing with other people, the ability to endure frustration, regulate moods and keep stress at bay. does not paralyze the ability to think, as well as empathize and pray emotional intelligence can be measured from several existing aspects.

Based on Goleman (Jumadi, 2020) emotional intelligence contains two dimensions, *The first*, is personal skills, namely skills in self-management which include the ability to, Self-awareness is the ability to be aware of all behavior that is carried out. Self-regulation is the ability to be able to manage oneself well. Self-motivation is the ability to be able to inspire oneself well. *The second*, Social skills, skills to manage relationships between humans in the environment including Sensitivity to others, and the ability to be able to feel what other people feel, namely a sense of caring and empathy. Social skills are the ability to relate to humans in their environment and places where they are. Meanwhile, according to Robins (2008) explains that emotional intelligence consists of five dimensions which include: Self-awareness, which is being aware of what you feel about yourself. Self-management, namely the ability to manage emotions and to encourage and manage oneself. Self-motivation, namely the ability to survive in the face of all events that cause setbacks and failures. Empathy is the ability to be able to feel what other people feel. Social skills are the ability to manage or deal with the emotions of others. Research (Karimi & Karimi, 2016) proves that emotional intelligence has a significant and positive effect on individual involvement in organizations. Research (Devi, 2016) shows that emotional intelligence has a positive influence on one's work and performance. The empirical evidence shows that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance (Dewi & Tenaya, 2017; Lassk & Shepherd, 2017; Wibowo, 2017). But the result of research (Jumadi, 2020) is that emotional intelligence does not have a positive effect on performance.

Figure 1. Framework Thinking

Hypothesis

1. Spiritual intelligence influences the performance of SMEs
2. Social intelligence influences the performance of SMEs
3. Emotional intelligence influences the performance of SMEs
4. Spiritual intelligence, social, and emotional intelligence, and affect the performance of SMEs

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a quantitative study with a population of small and medium enterprises. The sampling method is purposive sampling, by selecting subjects based on certain criteria set by the researcher. Sample selection is subjective in purposive sampling because researchers understand that the information needed can be obtained from certain target groups who can provide the desired information (Palinkas et al., 2015). This research was conducted using 90 samples. The tool used is a regression with IBM SPSS 25 software version and analysis with the previous average score being low in the very low, moderately high, high, and very high-class intervals.

$$\text{Structural Model: } Y = a + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + e$$

- Y = Performance
- a = constant
- b = Regression Coefficient
- X1 = Spiritual Intelligence
- X2 = Social Intelligence
- X3 = Emotional Intelligence
- e = standard error

Multiple linear regression analysis was used to test the existing hypotheses, namely to see the effect of the variables of spiritual intelligence on spiritual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and intelligence. The results of the regression test in the study are shown in the following table:

Table 1. Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3,802	1,865		2,039	0,045
Spiritual	0,247	0,089	0,287	2,768	0,007
Social	0,464	0,111	0,479	4,201	0,000
Emotional	0,062	0,094	0,072	0,658	0,512

$$Y = 3.802 + 0.247 X_1 + 0.464 X_2 + 0.062 X_3$$

Based on the multiple linear regression equation, it can be explained as follows: The constant value of 3.802 indicates that the performance of SMEs if spiritual, emotional, and intellectual intelligence is low. The spiritual intelligence coefficient value of 0.247 indicates that if spiritual intelligence increases, the performance of SMEs will also increase. The value of the social intelligence coefficient of 0.464 indicates that if social intelligence increases, the performance of SMEs will decrease. The coefficient of emotional intelligence is 0.062, which means that if emotional intelligence increases, it will improve the performance of SMEs.

Partial Hypothesis Test

Partial hypothesis testing is a statistical test to determine the significance of the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The conclusion in this test is by comparing the t value of the calculation results to the t table value or comparing the calculated probability value to the determined significance level.

Table 2. t-Statistic

Variables	t-Statistic	Prob
Spiritual	2,768	0,007
Social	4,201	0,000
Emotional	0,658	0,512

Based on the test partially using the t-test, the significance value of spiritual intelligence was 0.007. sig value. this is greater than 0.05 and less than 0.01 so it can be concluded that the spiritual intelligence variable has a positive effect on the performance of SMEs at a significance level of 10%. Based on this test, the hypothesis which states that Spiritual Intelligence affects SMEs performance is proven. This is consistent with the results of the study (Nggermanto, 2002; Supriyanto & Troena, 2012). According to (Akhtar et al., 2017) which states that spiritual intelligence is a means needed to identify and utilize limited resources to advance the work of an organization through its enthusiasm.

Based on the test partially using the t-test, the significance value of social intelligence was 0.000. sig value. This is smaller than 0.05 and 0.01 so it can be concluded that the social intelligence variable has a positive effect on the performance of SMEs at the level of 5% or with a significance of 10%. Based on this test, the hypothesis which states that social intelligence affects SME's performance is proven.

Based on the test partially using the t-test, the significance value of emotional intelligence was 0.512. sig value. This is greater than 0.05 and 0.01 so it can be concluded that the emotional intelligence variable does not have a positive effect on the performance of SMEs at either the 5% level or the 10% significance level. Based on these tests, the hypothesis which states that emotional intelligence affects the performance of SMEs is not proven. This is not following the results of research (Devi, 2016) shows that emotional intelligence has a positive influence on one's work and performance. Research (Karimi & Karimi, 2016) Research (Dewi & Tenaya, 2017; Lassk & Shepherd, 2017; Wibowo, 2017) states that emotional intelligence has a significant and positive influence on individual involvement in the organization. Improved performance can be achieved through high emotional control; Empirical evidence shows that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance. But the support the result of the research (Jumadi, 2020) emotional intelligence does not have a positive effect on performance.

The Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

The **Simultaneous** Hypothesis Test is a statistical test to determine the significance of the joint effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The conclusion in this test is by comparing the calculated f value to the f table value or comparing the calculated probability value to the determined significance level.

Table 3. F-Statistics

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	494,985	3	164,995	41,855	.000 ^b
Residual	339,015	86	3,942		
Total	834,000	89			

After being tested together using the f test, the significance value of spiritual intelligence, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence was 0.000. sig value. this is smaller than 0.05 and 0.01 so it can be concluded that the variables of spiritual intelligence, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence have a positive effect on the performance of SMEs at the level of 5% or with a significance of 10%. Based on this test, the hypothesis which states that spiritual, social, and emotional intelligence affects the performance of SMEs is proven.

Coefficient of Determination Test

The coefficient of determination (R^2) aims to determine how much the independent variable can explain and influence the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination is between zero and one. The value of R^2 means that the ability of the independent variables in explaining the dependent variable is limited.

Table 4. R^2

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.770 ^a	0,594	0,579	1,98546

The regression analysis used is multiple regression analysis so the coefficient of determination used is Adjusted R square (corrected coefficient of determination). The coefficient value obtained is 0.594. The value of determination becomes $0.594 \times 100\% = 59.4\%$. This indicates that the performance of SMEs is explained by 59.4% of variables of spiritual intelligence, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence, and the rest is explained by other variables that are not included in the model.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis with the partial test can be the conclusion; the variable of spiritual intelligence has a positive effect on the performance of SMEs with a sig value. of 0.007. The variable of social intelligence has a positive effect on the performance of SMEs but the variable of emotional intelligence does not have a positive effect on the performance of SMEs. Based on the analysis with the f-test the variables of spiritual intelligence, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence have a positive effect on the performance of SMEs.

SUGGESTION

Based on the foregoing, it can be suggested that in improving the performance of SMEs it is necessary to make efforts to improve spiritual intelligence, social intelligence, and emotional intelligence through various training or counseling by the relevant agencies or management.

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Cite this Article: Jumadi (2023). The Impact of Spiritual, Social, And Emotional Intelligence on the Performance of SMEs in the Covid-19 Pandemic. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(01), 109-115